

Impact of Advertisement on Consumer Purchase Decision: A Case Study of Cosmetic Industries in Mauritius

Author's Details

⁽¹⁾**Mahatma Jam Mercedes**

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: kellsmercedes05@gmail.com

⁽²⁾**Dr. Masood Hassan**

PhD, IoBM, Karachi, Pakistan and Visiting Faculty Greenwich, Karachi, Pakistan,

Email: masoodhassan1@hotmail.com (Corresponding Author)

Abstract

This study examines the impact of advertisement on consumer purchase decisions in the cosmetic industries of Mauritius. Most companies in Mauritius have very aggressive ways of advertising their products through effective promotional channels; this is due to the huge number of competitors in the market. Advertisements are helpful in creating perceptions among customers and it has been used for many years to influence consumer purchase decision both of these variables are combined to influence the consumer purchase decision. This study was conducted among 156 female and male individuals who use different cosmetic brands and are from different backgrounds. Both regression and correlation analyses were used. The results of this study are strong because all evidence mentions that advertising has a significant impact on consumer purchase decision.

Keywords: Advertisement, Purchase decision, Consumers, Cosmetic products.

Introduction

Background

Advertising can be related back to the dawn of known history. Archaeologists studying in Mediterranean countries have unearthed evidence indicating distinct events and offerings. The Romans constructed block walls to announce bum bouts, while the Phoenicians painted figures on enormous stones to sell their wares along rally routes. Modern advertising, on the other hand, is a far cry from those early efforts (Kotler & Armstrong 2012). Advertising is any paid type of non-personal communication about an organization, product, service, or idea by a specified sponsor. The paid component of this definition reflects the reality that advertising space or time must be purchased, with the exception of public service announcements, for which advertising space or time is supplied by the media. The quasi component suggests also that advertising uses mass media (e.g., television, radio, magazine, newspaper) to reach a considerable proportion of individuals. Except in direct response marketing, the impersonal nature of advertising implies that there is often no possibility for an instant reply from the message recipient (Belch & Belch, 2003). Advertising is recognized as a vital component of many marketers' promotional mix. This is because it may gain a greater number of users at a reduced cost. As a result, it is a premium method. It can be used to build brand images and representational tries to appeal to a company or brand, which is a key competency for enterprises that sell goods and services. There are five advertising features that influence customers' purchase decisions. Impressive, Understandable, Memorable, Creative, and Honest are some example (Kotler & Armstrong, 2012). Kumar (2014) also performed a study on the effect of advertisement on customer behaviors of various soap and washing powder brands. Ad memory, understandability, believability, and relevancy of commercials were found as markers of effect on customer behavior in his study. Advertising is a collection of techniques and methods used to inform and persuade clients to buy a product or service asserts. According to this definition, advertising serves two fundamental functions. To begin, it is a component or source of information that informs consumers when goods and services are available for purchase. Second, encourage customers to acquire a thing. Sharma (2009) also noted that trying to assess the effects of advertising is problematic and that indirect metrics concentrating on customer awareness might be employed. These are the measurements of exposure, awareness, and brand awareness. Companies must focus on one in order to be successful in the market. Marketers must address concerns such as how advertisements influence customer behavior and advertisements from a personal and societal standpoint when

building an advertising model (Mohan & Adinarayana, 2012). Consumer purchasing behavior is evolving at a fast rate, and firms must consider their customers' interests and preferences. To grasp the attitude of the audiences or consumers, adequate planning and approaches must be applied. In the contemporary era, practically everyone is impacted in one way by commercials and other forms of promotion. The public and private sectors, as well as both entities, have learned how vital communication with the target audience will certainly lead to success. Advertisement and other sorts of advertising methods are used effectively to sell and promote items and services. Advertising is vital in influencing dreams and supporting customers in making informed product and brand decisions. The impact of advertising can reach a wider audience, and the major purpose of advertising is to instruct customers about the items. The cosmetic industry in Mauritius is rapidly increasing. The majority of products used in Mauritius are from multinational brands. This business has gradually exceeded others in recent years as a result of a broad group of advertisements through which people become aware of and gather information which then encourages and convinces them to acquire a commodity. In recent years, cosmetic businesses have employed numerous promotional strategies to grab the market, such as social media, television messaging, airways, and billboards, to urge customers to repurchase these items. Companies utilize marketing methods to remind customers of their products and brand names. Because we are so involved in media day after day, it is simple in becoming cautious of any commercials (Agwa, 2012). A consumer is someone who buys various items or services for his or her own usage. The reasoning that precedes a consumer from defining a requirement to initiating possibilities and selecting a certain product and brand is referred to as the consumer purchasing decision. Consumer purchase decisions are impacted mostly by factors such as environment, family, and brand identification. And from the other side, awareness motivates buyers to purchase a particular product. As a result, cosmetic companies concentrate their efforts on areas influential to consumer purchasing decisions, such as a way of life, purchasing power, technology, and revenue. The beauty and individual consideration classes are regarded to be secure from swelling. In recent years, the Mauritius cosmetic sector has expanded considerably. Individuals' desire to look nice and be regarded in the community has a huge impact on their purchasing of cosmetic items. Men are growing more aware of the importance of affluence, vulnerable appeal, and wellbeing (Diagne, 2009). This research effort studies elements that affect purchasing decisions and dig into the involvement of advertising in determining consumer decisions. Most commercials employ enticing imagery and compelling words to persuade individuals' impressions of the product. Customers are lured to new ideas and unique ways to buy things and remember businesses. Advertisements play a crucial impact in influencing customers' buying intentions. Advertisements featuring endorsements help people remember the promoted goods. The buyer constantly associates the brand with the celebrity and can readily register the brand in their mind. According to Wells (2003), effective advertising was built on two dimensions first, they must achieve the objectives of the consumers by engaging them and delivering appropriate messages and secondly, the advertisements must achieve the advertiser's objectives. The emphasis of this particular thesis is placed on various forms of advertising and the impact those forms can have, individually and collectively, on the purchasing decisions of consumers. The buying behavior of consumers is largely influenced by a number of elements, the most prominent of which are culture, family, and the image of the brand. On the other side, the customer's familiarity with the brand is another factor that influences their decision to purchase a certain product. Because of this reality, the primary focus of cosmetic companies is marketing their products. This analysis also shed light on additional elements that can influence the buying behavior of customers such as lifestyle, purchasing power, technology, traditional culture, and income. These are only some of the topics that were discussed in the report. Because advertisers put in a significant amount of financial investment when promoting their goods, they make sure to maintain their focus on the aforementioned aspects in order to successfully impact the customer's mind with advertisements. The purchasing patterns of clients were also illuminated by this research to great effect. Individuals' perspectives and their patterns of purchase typically diverge from one another.

Problem Statement

Mauritius is a small island on which various cosmetics enterprises have established themselves, resulting in a broad selection of cosmetics brands. Many women endure worry, low self-esteem, and loss of self-confidence as a result of making commercials with exaggerated and unattainable beauty. Advertisement has shown to be a powerful communication medium, but businesses are still confused about how to use it and how it affects consumers' purchase decisions.

Research Significance

It is the goal of this study to determine how advertisements influence a user's buying decision. Consumers' buying decisions are examined in terms of how advertisements affect these factors. The findings of this study will aid readers in developing an effective marketing strategy to promote their cosmetic items by providing insight into the purchasing decisions of consumers.

Hypotheses

- H0- There is no link between advertising and consumer awareness.
- H1 – There is a link between advertising and consumer awareness.
- H0- There is no link between advertising and consumer perception.
- H2 – There is a link between advertising and consumer perception.
- H0- an advertisement will serve as a significant predictor and explain the difference in consumer purchase decisions in response to the cosmetic product.
- H3- an advertisement will not be a significant predictor and will not explain the difference in consumer purchase decisions in response to the cosmetic product.

Research Questions

- How does advertisement create awareness in consumers?
- Do advertisements shape perceptions in the mind of consumers?
- How does advertisement act as a significant predictor on consumer purchase decisions?

Research Objectives

- To identify the impact of advertisement on consumer awareness
- To identify the role of advertisement on building consumer perception
- To study the impact of advertisement as a significant predictor on consumer purchase decision.

Literature Review

A product's information is conveyed through advertising. According to these researchers, when a product's quality is advertised, it increases sales of lower-quality goods, which in turn raises the demand elasticity for those low-quality goods (Ozga, 1960). Obermiller and Sawyer (2010) found that more and earlier searches for the advertised brand were triggered by a good ad image rather than a negative one. Most crucially, the likeability of the ad image boosted brand preference. Emotional advertising influences consumers to search for information about the advertised brand early and then stop short of evaluating all other brands, increasing the likelihood that the advertised brand will be chosen. Advertisers' major objective is to reach out to their current and potential customers and deliver information about their products and services, as well as about the views and purchasing behavior of their current and potential customers (Ayanwale et al., 2005; Adelaar et al., 2003; Abideen & Saleem, 2011). Sender, encoder, messages, decoder, and recipient are the five steps in the advertising process. There are various stages to this procedure that are explained. There is a message that has been prepared and introduced to the audience. More than merely a message, advertising is a way of life. It's a rundown of various goods and companies. The advertiser initiates the transaction, and the recipient completes it (Schramm, 1995).

Awareness and Consumer Purchase Decision

A company's main goal is to reach out to possible customers and change their knowledge, attitudes, and buying habits. They spend a lot to keep people interested in their product. To do well, they must first know what makes their target groups act the way they do. The company's goal is to gather enough useful market data to create accurate buyer statuses and form a group of people who can talk to each other. It is the study of how people act as consumers. According to Romaniuk and Sharp's research article, people use different signals in different buying situations to remember the brand ad, and when the brand has unique features, it is more likely that any buyer will get it. This makes the brand strong. Advertising is always about letting a lot of people know about goods and services. For a consumer, advertising means making more people aware of what a product can do in different areas. Advertising affects how easy it is for people to get the products they want, which can meet the needs of the advertiser and lead to more sales. Sorina-Raula et al. (2012) say that when consumers make important decisions based on current information, they take a risk because this inaccurate information makes it hard for them to know which product will give them the most satisfaction or which brand really has the features they want. Because of this, buyers are usually more open to ads for 900 different brands when they are researching these brands. Because of this, if an advertiser can find them and talk to them, they are a better target.

Consumer Perception and Consumer Purchase Decision

Bigger brand shareholdings allow companies to spend more money on marketing to boost their brand's image value, which in turn increases the price of their sector peers, resulting in both companies gaining from this strategy. Advertisements have an impact on people's perceptions, and as a result, on their decisions and conduct. Cognition refers to a person's interpretation of advertising messaging. a person is aware of these thoughts via a wide range of senses and impressions as well as remembering and reasoning. Attracting new clients requires an in-depth knowledge of how people think and behave. People's culture is the first aspect that influences and shapes their purchasing decisions. Because of cultural influences, customers have strong opinions about products (Hye-Shin Kim, 2008). In the opinion of Rai (2013), there are numerous national and international brands with which consumers have a strong emotional connection. Because of their culture, lives, and surroundings, they hold certain beliefs. The influence of advertising on customer behavior is undeniable, to say the least. They are motivated to buy a specific product by advertisements that they see on television or in magazines. Creating brand associations through advertising, according to Heath and Ambler, is passive. As a result, decisions may be influenced more intuitively than consciously as a result of these linkages. Ehrenberg (2001) agrees that consumers often don't stick to a single brand, but rather have a collection of brands with which they have formed a relationship of some kind. As a result, advertising's function is to confirm the consumer's current tendency to buy it as one of the numerous acceptable brands, and gently push them to purchase it more frequently. Bashir and Aneeza (2009) stated that Customers are influenced by the attitudes of commercial advertisement personalities, and even this sort of advertisement influences them to buy a product at least once in their lives. It is widely accepted that consumers' conviction and trustworthiness are crucial to persuasion, and great advertising includes the primary features of the brand along with strategy, creativity, and execution.

Significant Predictor and Consumer Purchase Decision

Advertising has been considered for ages, although it wasn't as prominent as it is now until the twentieth-century Business leaders in the 19th century were focused on constructing the notion of perfectly competitive marketplaces, which claimed that consumers had fixed preferences for their products and that all of the information in the market was available. Advertising on items was seen to be a waste of resources an increase in production costs because consumers were not expected to respond in any manner (Bagwell, 2001). The number of cosmetics purchased by women rises in lockstep with their earnings. They also claimed that the advertising for the cosmetic product is to blame for the rise in prices. Customers want to improve their social standing and using a product can aid in this endeavor. Advertisement is thought to have an impact on the purchasing decisions of this social level (Bagwell, 2001). Advertising has a major impact on consumers' purchasing

decisions. Things with intrinsic qualities are usually easier to market. When a product is purchased, its attributes appear to be a mystery, and they must be learned via use. Businesses can influence people's behavior by changing their opinions through persuasive communication (such as advertisements). According to Ajzen and Fishbein (2005), attitudes are made up of a variety of factors, including a person's perceptions, feelings, and social norms. These three methods have helped consumers discover their genuine habits. Cognitive, emotional, and conative components all play a role in determining whether or not a person intends to engage in the desired behavior after learning about it. When making a purchase, the expressive set refers to the list of possibilities that instantly spring to mind during the decision-making process. Almost every time a customer needs services, they go to a business that sells only one brand.

Advertisement and Factors Influencing

A creative effort to influence the consumer's desire to purchase a specific product and alter or create the consumer's perception of a product is the goal of advertising in the first place. An announcement appeal is a supplier's tool for stimulating the rationale for purchase in the mind of the customer. A combination of reasoned and passionate prayer is employed in the announcement. Emotional prayers fulfill the mental, emotional, and social needs of the customer whereas rational prayers focus on the product's advantages and potential difficulties. As stated previously (Gunjah, 2012). An announcement is a way to get your message through to your audience. They argued that people's coping behaviors were heavily influenced by their culture because everyone has unique desires and trends based on their own cultural traditions. A lot of people are touched by announcements, and organizations are attempting to reach as many people as possible with their messages. In order to promote their products, companies utilize a combination of above- and below-the-line methods. Increasingly, companies are creating content that appeals to both teenage girls and guys (Nidhi, 2008). Advertisers are now looking at the amount of mass media channels and methods of communication that allow them to reach customers quickly and easily in the ultramodern era. Technology has also provided guests with an abundance of information and the ability to pick and choose what they like. Advertisers' ability to create brand awareness and condition customers' brains to make final purchase decisions is becoming more difficult as customers have more power over the items and information they consume (Raju, 2013).

Impact of Advertisement

The purpose of advertising is to communicate a message to a big number of different people. This approach makes it possible to communicate with a large number of people. Understanding the role that advertising plays in driving sales is highly important to achieving success and is a useful technique for raising both brand awareness and sales. There is a correlation between the amount of advertising spent and the number of products sold (Abiodun, 2011). People's actions are influenced by publicity, and as a result, their interest in buying particular products grows. According to the findings of the research, researchers found that customers' memories were affected by repeated exposure to commercials, which in turn led to customers making additional purchases of the product (Pope, 2009). In spite of the fact that men are with women, research indicates that this market is extremely competitive and is largely controlled by women. It is common knowledge that the customer is at the very top of the food chain, and marketers are always searching for novel approaches to persuade a larger number of new customers. These elements are not limited to, the purchasing patterns, preferences, tastes, likes, and dislikes of consumers; as a result, businesses need to adjust their marketing strategies and policies accordingly. When it comes to their purchases, people in this industry place a significant amount of importance on quality. Because of how well it works, the brand has garnered the devotion of its customers. These clients have such a deep emotional commitment to the brands that they are willing to wait even if the product they want is not yet on the market. Nevertheless, despite the fact that consumers are getting more knowledgeable about companies, they are still the ones who are in charge of making the final choice (Desai, 2014).

Advertising Techniques

Cosmetic advertisements and promotions employ a variety of techniques. Some of them are explained (OAKLEY, 2009):

- Young people respond best to advertising that evokes a desire in them to act. This type of ad uses catchphrases and taglines to pique the interest of potential customers. The phrases "most beautiful me" and "real perfection must be flawed" come to mind as two such instances. There are three elements that most advertisements rely on to entice you to make a purchase: perfection, sex appeal, and prestige (OAKLEY, 2009). Endorsement by a Celebrity: Young people, in particular, find this form of advertising quite effective. However, it is unclear whether or not using well-known personalities in advertisements increases consumer confidence in the brand being advertised (OAKLEY, 2009).
- Social responsibility ads: Many cosmetics brands, like Dove, are linked to good things for society. A survey found that women who use cosmetics feel confident because these brands market themselves as making people feel good about themselves (OAKLEY, 2009).

Marshall named three well-known formal psychology models: economic models, social psychology models, and models of how people make decisions about what to buy. After studying these models, researchers made new models of how people buy things based on different assumptions. More accurate are the Howard-Sheth model, the Nicosia model, and the theory of rational behavior. The models that these scholars made give us theoretical frameworks for understanding how people make decisions and how they buy things in the future. The "sensory input" conceptual framework, which professor Howard came up with in 1963 and then revised with Xie Si in 1969, tries to explain why people will buy the same brand or product more than once. This framework shows how people make decisions about what to buy based on four main factors: stimuli or input variables, events in the environment, internal variables, and responses or output variables.

Conceptual Framework

The goal of this study is to find out how advertising affects people's decisions about what cosmetics to buy. It will look at how people know about advertisements, how they think about them, and how they affect how people decide what to buy.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

No matter how much the ad costs, it has a direct effect on the consumer. It tends to make people more aware of the product and encourages them to buy it. The advertisement affects how people think of the brands, whether in a good or bad way. Our study's design tries to figure out how advertisement affects customers' awareness, perception, and a unique aspect of a consumer's decision to buy. This model starts by explaining the factors that affect a consumer's decision to buy something. It then shows the right way to use advertising for men and women while keeping awareness and perception in mind. This will ultimately meet the needs of consumers, make them want to buy a certain product more, and encourage them to reprice these products.

Methodology

The goal of this chapter is to describe a methodical approach to organizing data collecting, dimensioning, and analysis for the purposes of exploration. You'll find all you need to know about performing the research in this document. When scientists perform exploratory research, they increase their chances of obtaining data relevant to today's world while also helping them plan how to conduct their studies. The research relies on quantitative data collected through an online survey that was based on empirical substantiation.

Data Collection, Population and Sample Size

An investigation is a coordinated effort to deal with attack issues and generate new data that is generally material (Dawson, 2002). For this inquiry, researchers focused on Port Louis, Mauritius' capital and most populated city. 150 people of all ages who live in Port Louis were surveyed for this study. I utilized an arbitrary slicing method when presiding over the questionnaire. Primary data was gathered from a replier in the research region and from interviews with repliers. Data was gathered through the use of online questionnaire. It was based on primary data. There was a two-part structure to the questions (Section I and II). Section I was designed to collect data on a variety of demographic variables, such as gender, age, and level of education. Section II was created to measure the general knowledge of the responders about the advertisement and the effect of the advertisement broken into sections. The researcher sends out online questionnaires to each of the participants, thanking them for their time and expressing gratitude for their involvement. Participants were given the chance to complete questionnaires at their leisure by the researcher.

Statistic Technique

Data were entered into SPSS and then analyzed. Statistical program for social sciences is referred to as SPSS and is used by academics to carry out statistical procedures. Correlation analysis is used to determine the nature of the correlation between the independent and dependent variables.

Model

The data collected will be analyzed using a one-sample t-test. An index will be created from the sum of the calculated means for each domain in order to show the effect of advertisements on consumer purchasing decisions for cosmetics products.

Analysis and Result

Graphical Analysis

Table 1
Gender

	Ranks		
	Gender	N	Mean Rank
Advertising_Buying_Behaviour	Male	71	73.77
	Female	84	81.58
	Total	155	

Table 1.1
Test Statistics^{a,b}

	Advertising_Buying_Behaviour
Kruskal-Wallis H	1.169
Df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.280

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
b. Grouping Variable: Gender

Gender shows that there is no significant difference between each range although the mean shows that more female has advertising buying behavior than male. The mean rank was eighty-one (81) for female and seventy-three (73) for male.

Table 2

Age

Ranks			
	Age	N	Mean Rank
Advertising_Buying_Behaviour	19-25	44	78.18
	26-32	61	80.93
	33-39	26	69.83
	40-49	15	74.30
	50 and above	9	87.06
	Total	155	

Table 2.1
Test Statistics^{a,b}

Advertising_Buying_Behaviour	
Kruskal-Wallis H	1.595
Df	4

When it comes to advertising and making purchases, age doesn't matter all that much. Advertisements have an impact on people of all ages, according to a study. The average rating for each age group was greater than fifty (50). People over the age of fifty (50) had the highest average score, coming in at number eighty-seven (87).

Table 3

Qualification

Ranks			
	Qualification	N	Mean Rank
Advertising_Buying_Behaviour	Matric	16	63.00
	Inter	31	55.24
	Graduate	76	85.70
	Masters and above	32	89.27
	Total	155	

Table 3.1
Test Statistics^{a,b}

Advertising_Buying_Behaviour	
Kruskal-Wallis H	14.053
Df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.003

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Qualification

As the table suggest there is no significant difference found between the levels of qualification in the means comparison of advertising buying behavior. All means were above 50 in the mean rank.

Table 4

Marital Status

Ranks			
	Marital status	N	Mean Rank
Advertising_Buying_Behaviour	Single	98	80.02
	Married	57	74.54
	Total	155	

Table 4.1
Test Statistics^{a,b}

Advertising_Buying_Behaviour	
Kruskal-Wallis H	.539
Df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.463

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Marital status

Marital status also shows no difference but interestingly people who are single are more affected by advertisement. Or have more advertising buying behavior.

Table 5
Children

Ranks			
	Children	N	Mean Rank
Advertising_Buying_Behaviour	None	80	83.41
	1 to 3	42	77.64
	4 to 6	22	74.05
	7 and above	11	47.95
	Total	155	

Table 5.1

Test Statistics^{a,b}

Advertising_Buying_Behaviour	
Kruskal-Wallis H	6.283
Df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.099

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Children

According to the results of the poll, the majority of respondents did not have children, and those without children were the most likely to be influenced by advertising or engage in advertising-related purchasing behavior. Even yet, the average rank was 83, while the lowest-ranked families had seven or more children and a rank of forty-seven. (47).

Table 6
Employment Status

Ranks			
	Employment Status	N	Mean Rank
Advertising_Buying_Behaviour	Employed	62	87.60
	Unemployed	22	67.98
	Student	44	68.92
	None	27	78.91
	Total	155	

Table 6.1

Test Statistics^{a,b}

Advertising_Buying_Behaviour	
Kruskal-Wallis H	5.766
Df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.124

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Employment status

People who are students, unemployed, or both are less likely to be influenced by advertisements while making a purchasing decision, according to their employment status. We can see that when someone has a job, they are more susceptible to advertising's effect since they have the means to make purchases.

Table 7
Religious Background

Ranks			
	Religious background	N	Mean Rank
Advertising_Buying_Behaviour	Christian	95	72.07
	Muslim	17	71.94
	Hindu	19	84.84
	None of the above	23	97.98
	Total	154	

Table 7.1

Test Statistics^{a,b}

	Advertising_Buying_Behaviour
Kruskal-Wallis H	7.061
Df	3
Asymp. Sig.	.070

a. Kruskal Wallis Test
b. Grouping Variable: Religious background

There was a clear divide between Christians and Muslims in the responses to the questionnaires. Those whose religions were mentioned in advertisements scored best on a mean scale.

Reliability Test

Descriptive Analysis

The data shows that no matter what whether gender, age, marital status, number of children or religion there is little or no significant difference in terms of advertising buying behaviors.

Reliability Analysis

The reliability analysis was done through Cronbach's Alpha test.

Table 8

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	144	92.9
	Excluded ^a	11	7.1
	Total	155	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Table 8.1
Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.528	16

Case processing summary shows a big difference between the cases which were validated and which were excluded. Ninety-two percent (92%) was validated while seven percent (7%) was excluding. The reliability statistics shows that there is no significant difference.

Inferential Analysis

Research shows that commercials have a significant impact on consumers' purchasing decisions for cosmetic items; therefore this fact can be generalized and applied to a larger population. Static also lends Mauritius as a whole a degree of generalizability.

Hypotheses Assessment Summary

Since my data showed no significant difference it means that the hypothesis was:

- H0- There is no link between advertising and consumer awareness - reject
- H1 – There is a link between advertising and consumer awareness -accept
- H0- There is no link between advertising and consumer perception -reject
- H2 – There is a link between advertising and consumer perception - accept
- H0- an advertisement will serve as significant predictor and discuss the difference in consumer purchase decisions in response to the cosmetic advertisement - reject
- H3- an advertisement will not be a significant predictor and will not discuss the difference in consumer purchase decisions in response to the cosmetic advertisement – accept

Conclusion

Vendors rely on advertising as a key means of attracting clients to their goods and services. The organization's products needed to be advertised at this moment in order to draw in new customers. Getting your message out there requires a variety of different types of advertising media. For this reason, a study was conducted to examine the primary components of consumer advertising that may entice customers and encourage them to buy. In order to have a substantial impact on customer purchase decisions, marketers need to use more innovative advertising strategies. To avoid consumer aggravation, advertisement length and frequency of repeat should be lowered.

Consumers' purchase decisions are influenced by two key aspects, according to the findings of this study Male and female subjects took part in the study, which was performed in Mauritius. In order to investigate the link between advertising influence and customer purchasing decisions, a survey was conducted and statistical tools were applied. Advertisement has been found to influence consumers' purchasing decisions in the poll. Companies in cosmetic advertising and marketing on the island will benefit greatly from this study's conclusions.

Limitations

According to the study's problem statement, advertising portrays women and men as unrealistically beautiful create anxiety and low self-esteem in many people. Due to a large number of replies necessary, this study also had a limited time frame. Only 155 of the 215 persons who received the questionnaire via various social media channels answered. There were 144 replies that were accepted and 11 that were denied.

Recommendations

- To catch the attention of cosmetic product buyers, an innovative method of advertising should be used.
- Consumer purchasing decisions should be consistently considered when developing the cosmetic products' advertising message.
- More time should be given to the researcher to collect responses for effective results.
- The use of unrealistic and unattainable images in advertisements should be reduced, and more natural images should be used to boost self-esteem.

References

Abideen, Z. U., & Latif, A. (2011). Do brand extensions affect consumer attitude: an empirical experience-with reference to Pakistani consumers. *Journal of Applied Business Research (JABR)*, 27(2),19-36

- Adelaar, T., Chang, S., Lancendorfer, K. M., Lee, B., & Morimoto, M. (2003). Effects of media formats on emotions and impulse buying intent. *Journal of Information Technology*, 18(4), 247-266.
- Agwa, E. (2012). Generation x and y adaption of internet and internet banking. *International journal of online marketing*, 68-81.
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (2005). The influence of attitudes on behavior. The handbook of attitudes. *Red. D. Albarracin, BT Johnson & MP Zanna. Mahwah: Erlbaum*, 173-221.
- Ayanwale, A.B., Alimi, T. & Aya, M.A. (2005).The Influence of Advertising on Consumer Brand Preference, *Journal of Social Sciences*, 10(1), 9-16.
- Bagwell, K. (2001). The economic analysis of advertising. *American economic review*. 2(81), 224-239.
- Baheti, G., Jain, R. K., & Jain, N. (2012). The Impact of Advertising Appeals on Consumer Buying Behavior. *International Journal of Research in commerce & Management*.
- Banerjee, B., & Bandyopadhyay, S. (2003). Advertising competition under consumer inertia. *Marketing Science*, 22(1), 131-144.
- Dawson, T. (2002). Practical research methods: New Delhi: UBS. *Publishers Distributors, India*.
- Diagne, S. & (2009). Consumptions of cosmetic attitude and motivations. *Journal of consumer marketing*, 26, 97-109.
- Hype-shin, J.J. (2008). The effects of facial image and cosmetic usage on the perception of brand personality. *Journal of fashion marketing and management*.
- Kotwal, N., Gupta, N., & Devi, A. (2008). Impact of TV advertisements on buying pattern of adolescent girls. *Journal of Social sciences*, 16(1), 51-55.
- Ozga, S. A. (1960). Imperfect markets through lack of knowledge. *The quarterly journal of Economics*, 29-52.
- Pope, D. (2003). Making sense of advertisements. *History matters: The US survey course on the Web*.
- Raju, D. D. (2013). The Role of Advertising in Consumer Decision Making. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*. 14 (4).
- Schiffman, L.G. (1993). Consumer Behavior, Prentice Hall International, London
- Schramm, W. (1995). How Communication Works in the Process & Effect of Mass Communications (pp 3-26) Urban.
- Sorina-Raula, G., Liviu, C., & Georgeta-Mădălina, M. (2012). The role of advertising in the purchase decision process. *Analele Universitatii Din Oradea*, 17(4), 897-1574.
- Wells, W., B. and Moriarty S., (2003), "How Advertising Works", Advertising Principles and Practice, Pearson Education, 6th Edition, 153-179.
- Wells, W., Burnett, J., & Moriarty, S. (2000). Advertising principles and practice.5th edition. USA: Prentice Hall.